

Report of the webinar sessions “Towards a Global Strategic Research Agenda (SRA)”

Date: 26/01/2026 (9:30 to 12:30 CET) & 28/01/2026 (21:00 to 00:00 CET)

Modality: remote (Teams)

Facilitators: Samantha De Gottal, Lena Vlamincx, Ria Nouwen (FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, BE), Baldissera Giovani, Jassmine Zorrilla (Euphresco Network Office, Int.)

This document reports on the contents of both sessions of the webinar “Towards a Global Strategic Research Agenda”. As both sessions were identical, the contents of the presentations are only summarized once. The input on the questionnaire and open discussion is collectively reported below.

The proposed agenda was followed during the meeting and can be found below.

AGENDA

0:00	Welcome (15 min)	
0:00	Welcome & Introduction	Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)
0:15	Intro to EUPHRESKO III & the SRA (30 min)	
0:15	EUPHRESKO III-project	Baldissera Giovani/ Jassmine Zorrilla (ENO, Int.)
0:30	Outline, Timing & Progress of the SRA	Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)
0:45	Presenting SRA 0.1 (30 min)	
0:45	SRA 0.1: Introduction	Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)
1:00	SRA 0.1: Scope	Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)
1:15	Break	
1:30	Discussion & Feedback on SRA 0.1 (75 min)	
1:30	Live Input on Questionnaire	
1:50	Open Discussion	
2:45	Next steps (15 min)	
2:45	Future Development of the SRA	Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)
3:00	End	

1.1 List of participants

Session 1 - 26/01/2026 (9:30 to 12:30 CET)

Name	Affiliation
Anthoine Géraldine	Direction régionale de l'alimentation, de l'agriculture et de la forêt (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR)
Aveskamp Maikel	Netherlands Food and Consumer Products Safety Authority (NVWA, NL)
Baser Nuray	International Center for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies (CIHEAM-Bari, Int.)
Boyen Jens	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA, Int.)
Capieau Kristof	Chief Plant Health Officer for the Swedish Board of Agriculture (CPHO Sweden, SE)
Clover Gerard	Forestry Commission (UKFC, GB)
Cruz Leonor	Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV, PT)
Damsgaard Lannig Henry	Chief Plant Health Officer for the Danish Ministry of Food, Agricultural and Fisheries (CPHO Denmark, DK)
De Gottal Samantha	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Giovani Baldissera	Euphresco Network Office (ENO, Int.)
Guenter Joanna	Main Inspectorate of Plant Health and Seed Inspection (MIPHSI, PL)
Gundelach Rannes Christine	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (MFAFD, DK)
Iovinella Immacolata	Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification (CREA, IT)
Jakobs Inga	Water, Growth and Inclusion International Water Management Institute (IWMI, Int.), Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research (CGIAR, Int.)
Kaiser Marco	Bioreba (Bioreba, CH)
Kayattukandy Balan Rebijith	Plant Health and Environment Laboratory, Ministry for Primary Industries (PHEL-MPI, NZ)
Magdolenová Marta	Chief Plant Health Officer for the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development Republic of Poland (CPHO Poland, PL)
Malm Maarja	Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture (MRAA, EE)
Masci Alberto	Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies (MAFFP, IT)
Mazzoni Valerio	Edmund Mach Foundation (EMF, IT)
Munaut Françoise	European Commission Directorate-General for Health & Food Safety (DG SANTE, Int.)
Nam Kiwoong	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE, FR)
Nõmmik Marge	Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture (MRAA, EE)
Nouwen Ria	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
O'Hanlon Richard	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM, IE)
Oronje MaryLucy	Centre for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI, Int.)
Souza Richards Rose	International Seed Federation (ISF, Int.)
Steinmüller Silke	Julius-Kühn Institut (JKI, DE)

Tello Marisa	National Institute for Agricultural Research and Food Technology, Spanish National Research Council (INIA-CSIC, ES)
Teulon David	Plant and Food Research (PFR, NZ)
Topitschnig Christina	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES, AT)
Vlaminck Lena	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Windstam Sofia	Swedish Board of Agriculture (SJV, SE)
Zorrilla Fontanesi Jassmine	Euphresco Network Office (ENO, Int.)

Apologies: Babar Bajwa (CABI, Int.)

Session 2 - 28/01/2026 (21:00 to 00:00 CET)

Name	Affiliation
Collins Susie	Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry (DAFF, AU)
Davie Kim	Science and Advice for Scottish Agriculture (SASA, GB)
Day Brittany	Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA, CA)
De Gottal Samantha	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Giovani Baldissera	Euphresco Network Office (ENO, Int.)
Goldsmith Juliet	Caribbean Agricultural Health and Food Safety Agency (CAHFSa, Int.)
Gomez Grande Pablo	National Institute for Agricultural Research and Food Technology, Spanish National Research Council (INIA-CSIC, ES)
Gosai Riten	Pacific Community (SPC, Int.)
Hietala Ari	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO, NO)
Muller Giovanna	International Potato Center (CIP, Int.)
Nam Kiwoong	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE, FR)
Nouwen Ria	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)
Pappas Jaime	Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry (DAFF, AU)
Park Ikju	International Association for the Plant Protection Sciences (IAPPS, Int.)
Paudel Sulav	International Association for the Plant Protection Sciences (IAPPS, Int.)
Pita-Romero Herrero José Luis	National Institute for Agricultural Research and Food Technology, Spanish National Research Council (INIA-CSIC, ES)
Stippel Sairah	Ministerie van Landbouw, Veeteelt en Visserij van Suriname (MLVVS, SR)
Vlaminck Lena	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment (FPS Health, BE)

Apologies: Jassmine Zorrilla Fontanesi (ENO, Int.)

1.2 Welcome & Introduction – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) opened the session by welcoming all participants to the webinar dedicated to discussing the draft Global Strategic Research Agenda (SRA 0.1). She explained that this session forms part of a broader consultation phase intended to gather feedback from EUPHRESKO III partners and advisors, and Euphresco network members. Ms De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) outlined the agenda and explained the practical arrangements (see above).

Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) highlighted that the webinar was being recorded to ensure that all comments and questions could be revisited during the drafting phase.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) introduced the presenters: representatives of the Euphresco Network Office (Ms. Jassmine Zorrilla and Mr. Baldissera Giovanni), as well as colleagues from FPS Health Belgium (Ms. Lena Vlamincx and Ms. Ria Nouwen) who assisted in facilitating the webinar.

1.3 EUPHRESKO III-project – Jassmine Zorrilla (ENO, Int.)

Ms. Zorrilla (ENO, Int.) detailed the structure, purpose and evolution of EUPHRESKO III. Her presentation covered:

- Definition of research coordination across four pillars: identifying research priorities, commissioning/ funding transnational projects, project implementation, and valorization of results.
- Fragmentation challenges within Europe and globally, including fragmentation across research funding bodies, research providers, and between policymakers and research structures.
- Development of Euphresco from its establishment in 2006 through EUPHRESKO I and II, transitioning from a Western European network to a global platform aimed at research coordination for phytosanitary issues.
- Global expansion under EUPHRESKO III, including involvement of 35 project partners representing regions around the world, each supported by regional and discipline champions.
- Work packages, particularly Work Package 2 (development of the SRA), WP3 (joint transnational calls), and WP4 (building governance for a future global phytosanitary research coordination network).
- Consultation achievements, including engagement with more than 2,100 stakeholders across all regions and disciplines, and the creation of regional/disciplinary consultation reports that underpin the SRA.

1.4 Outline, Timing & Progress of the SRA – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) explained the conceptual foundations of the SRA and why such a strategic document is needed at the global level. She gave the general definition for a SRA, being a roadmap that outlines research priorities, gaps and questions, facilitating coordination among funders, policymakers, researchers and industry. She emphasized the dual purpose of the Global Plant Health SRA: creating a shared vision for global plant health research and helping the Euphresco network expand its visibility and relevance at the global level.

She provided a structured explanation of the SRA development timeline, beginning with initial consultations in early 2025, continuing with bilateral meetings in September–October, and leading to the first written draft in December 2025 (SRA 0.1). The current webinar forms part of the step of collecting structured feedback on this initial draft.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) also explained the early steps towards the development of the Global Plant Health SRA, including a preliminary structure and a 1-pager. The latter consisted of a “tree visual” developed early in the process, representing the conceptual structure of the SRA: UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as the roots; global and regional priorities as branches; and objectives as leaves. She emphasized the document’s intended dynamic nature and the link with the visual; like a tree is able to shed its branches and leaves to grow new ones, as such the dynamic component of the SRA will allow for new priorities and objectives to adapt to emerging plant threats.

Ms. Topitschnig (AGES, AT) asked whether the visual is being prepared in parallel and will be integrated into the final SRA. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) explained that it is planned to include a visual in the final SRA as it will help to bring structural clarity, and that the best option on how to integrate it still has to be determined.

1.5 Presenting SRA 0.1 – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) presented the content of the draft (SRA 0.1) that was shared with the participants in advance. She began by highlighting the differences in structure between this draft and the preliminary structures created at the start of the development process. For instance, the addition of a glossary section was discussed as the necessity for clear terminology became apparent during the consultation process. Another example is the shift from priorities towards broader themes within which objectives can be incorporated. The final draft contained four main components as a result: the glossary, introduction, scope, and themes & objectives.

- Glossary: this section is needed to clarify exactly what is meant with specific terms (especially within the ‘Scope’ and ‘Themes & Objectives’ sections) due to inconsistent terminology across regions. Where possible, this section contains internationally defined or adapted definitions from the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), United Nations (UN), World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Union

for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN). When international definitions were lacking, the glossary relied on scientific literature and dictionary entries.

- Introduction: covers the importance of global plant health, the threats plant health faces and the rationale for research coordination and collaboration on a global scale. In addition, this section covers the aims of the SRA, links to One Health and SDGs, and evaluation and adaptation of the document. The latter refers to the aforementioned dynamic component, which gives the document an adaptive nature, in addition to its evaluation procedure. This procedure is yet to be developed but will rely on impact indicators and best practice approaches to ensure objectives remain relevant and feasible.

- Scope: clarifies what is in and out of scope for the SRA. The scope sets the boundaries of the themes and objectives to ensure that the SRA maintains focus on its core purpose: providing foundation for coordinated research, defining shared priorities and guiding international collaboration. Out-of-scope items include purely commercial breeding objectives or agricultural areas unrelated to plant pests. In-scope items include transnational phytosanitary research needs, cross-border challenges, and plant-health-related industry involvement (seed, biotechnology, diagnostics).

- Themes & objectives: 12 themes (listed below) derived from an AI-supported thematic analysis of consultation reports and bilateral meeting outputs:

1. Breeding & Genetic Resistance
2. Capacity-building & Infrastructure Development
3. Climate Change & Resilience
4. Collaboration & Knowledge Sharing
5. Diagnostics, Surveillance & Early Warning
6. Data Science & Digital Revolution for Plant Health
7. Economics, Public Acceptance & Science-Policy Translation
8. Pest Pathways, Surveillance & Risks
9. Plant Health In A One Health Context
10. Preparedness, Response & Recovery
11. Sustainable Pest Management & Biocontrol
12. Trade Harmonization, Regulation & Facilitation

An example objective was also generated via this analysis for the 1st theme, however Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) clarified this was purely illustrative. The objectives will be further established after a more complete analysis and additional input from plant health stakeholders. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) also noted there was a mistake in SRA 0.1 where only 10 themes were listed under the scope section. This discrepancy is the result of 2 ‘transversal’ themes (theme 7 and 9) being added at a later stage of the development process. Although the subjects covered by these themes recurred several times within the consultation, it was not yet clear how to integrate them in SRA 0.1. Consequently, they were added as 2 additional themes for the time being.

1.6 Discussion & Feedback on SRA 0.1 – Lena Vlaminck (FPS Health, BE)

Participants completed a series of poll questions addressing terminology, clarity of scope, structure of themes, and the dynamic component. After all polls were completed, an open discussion followed, moderated by Ms. Vlaminck (FPS Health, BE) where the results of each poll were discussed. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions, express opinions and provide feedback on each of the poll questions. These deeper insights will be considered for the development of the first full version of the Global Plant Health SRA (SRA 1.0).

Question 1: How clear is the overall purpose of the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) as described in the draft?

Results summary: 73.3% of participants indicated the purpose was very clear, 23.3% said it was clear but could be more concise, and 3.3% found it somewhat unclear.

Session 1:

Mr. Capieau (CPHO Sweden, SE) explained that although the overall purpose of the SRA was understandable, he found the introductory section confusing. According to him, the beginning of the document seemed to signal a focus on global phytosanitary needs, while the presentation earlier in the session suggested a shift towards a broader plant health framing. This mismatch created uncertainty about the intended scope.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) agreed with Mr. Capieau’s interpretation and confirmed that the text should indeed be aligned to reflect “plant health” rather than “phytosanitary needs,” as this reflected the direction favored by most stakeholders during the consultation process.

Session 2:

No comments on Question 1.

Question 2: How clear and appropriate did you find the terminology used throughout the draft Strategic Research Agenda?

Results summary: 66.7% of participants found the terminology clear, 27.3% found it very clear, and 6.1% said it was somewhat unclear.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) raised two main issues. Firstly, like Mr. Capieau, she noted that the document used the term “phytosanitary” inconsistently and that this required clarification. Secondly, she asked whether pesticides were included within the scope of the SRA. Since this question had appeared repeatedly within Euphresco discussions, she recommended that the final document state clearly whether or not the SRA intended to address pesticide-related matters.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) explained that the issue of pesticides would need further internal discussion. She assured that the final version of the SRA would clarify the position of pesticides explicitly in relation to the scope.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added that the glossary currently only included terms already used in the document, which explained the absence of certain terms such as pesticides. As the SRA develops further and more themes and objectives are added, the glossary would naturally expand.

Mr. Giovani (ENO, Int.) commented that he appreciated aligning the glossary with international bodies such as IPPC, FAO or WHO as it lends the document legitimacy. However, he cautioned that these organizations operate in very specific contexts. Definitions should therefore be checked carefully to ensure they remain meaningful when applied to the Global Plant Health SRA.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) agreed and noted that it had already proved challenging to find definitions that aligned both with international usage and with the way the SRA intended to use the terms.

Session 2:

To stimulate discussion, Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) suggested sharing remarks from the previous webinar session. In response to this, Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) explained that finding internationally agreed definitions had not been straightforward. In several cases, the team needed to use dictionary-based interpretations or develop adapted definitions.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added additional context from the previous session. She recounted that participants had welcomed the use of terminology from UN and other international organizations, but warned that those definitions must be checked carefully so that their meanings fully align with the global plant health SRA. She emphasized that the team would review all terms one-by-one to ensure contextual correctness in the next version.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) confirmed that this would also apply to the inconsistent use of “phytosanitary” and “plant health.” Ms. Vlaminck (FPS Health, BE) expanded on this point, explaining that based on extensive feedback from regional champions and consultation meetings, a shift toward the broader term plant health appeared appropriate. Several participants indicated agreement.

Question 3: To what extent does the current scope meet your expectations?

Results summary: 74.3% said the scope mostly meets their expectations, 17.1% said it fully meets expectations, 5.7% said it minimally meets expectations, and 2.9% said it partially meets expectations.

Session 1:

Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) explained that he was one of the participants who had selected “minimally.” He attributed this mainly to the unresolved ambiguity between phytosanitary versus plant health terminology. He argued that either the SRA should commit to focusing on plant health, accompanied by a strong motivation for broadening, or the team should narrow down the scope of the SRA.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) observed that this was the third intervention raising the same concern, suggesting the need to give the phytosanitary–plant health distinction its own section within the scope chapter. This could ensure that readers fully understood what the SRA intended to cover and why.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) welcomed Ms. Nouwen’s suggestion and asked Mr. Aveskamp to explain in his own terms how he differentiated plant health from phytosanitary matters. Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) responded that, for NPPOs, phytosanitary work is fundamentally concerned with regulated organisms. He noted that while NPPOs generally prefer a phytosanitary focus, many stakeholders engaged in the wider consultation process represent broader interests. This divergence likely explains the push to adopt a more inclusive plant health framing. Ms. Munaut (DG SANTE, Int.) also provided her definition in the chat stating the following: “Pests that are not regulated yet, might be, or are already emerging ones”.

Ms. Vlaininck (FPS Health, BE) pointed out that if the SRA moves towards a plant health scope, the phytosanitary component will still inevitably be included. She highlighted that

feedback from bilateral meetings across regions and disciplines overwhelmingly favored broadening.

Mr. Giovani (ENO, Int.) added historical and strategic context. He explained that Euphresco was originally created to optimise research funding and provisions of research funding in phytosanitary research. The focus originally remained on regulated organisms because other networks already existed to address broader plant health topics. However, emerging pests, which lie outside traditional phytosanitary frameworks, had also been part of Euphresco's remit. Whether to keep the scope narrow or broaden it should be seen as a strategic decision related to the network's evolution, membership, and long-term mandate.

Session 2:

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) recalled that a few people in the previous section highlighted some concerns regarding the scope, and that this was largely linked to unresolved questions around the breadth of the scope. Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) observed that, judging from earlier reactions, the group in Session 2 generally supported a broader scope.

Question 4: How clear is the scope of the SRA as described in the draft?

Results summary: 61.8% found the scope very clear, 26.5% said it was clear but could be more concise, 5.9% said it was somewhat unclear, and 5.9% voted for ‘other’.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) noted that she had found the scope “somewhat unclear” because the draft neither explicitly used nor explained the absence of the IPPC Strategic Framework. Given that the IPPC was presented in the earlier “pyramid” slide showing global governance levels as presented by Ms. Zorrilla (ENO, Int.) in the section explaining the EUPHRESKO III project, she expected either a reference to the framework or a justification for omitting it.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) confirmed that the SRA had not been drafted based on the IPPC Strategic Framework and agreed that the final version needed to clarify why.

Mr. Giovanni (ENO, Int.) responded directly to Ms. Anthoine’s point. He explained that referencing the IPPC Strategic Framework within the SRA is not simply a technical choice, but a political one. Only countries, acting via the IPPC governing bodies, have the mandate to decide whether global phytosanitary research coordination should align with the IPPC’s strategic directions. Euphresco can only insert an alignment with the IPPC Strategic Framework in case there is an international political mandate to do so. In response to Mr. Giovanni, Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) added that she found this explanation inconsistent with another part of the SRA. The draft did reference the United Nations SDGs. Ms. Anthoine argued that if referencing SDGs is appropriate and acceptable, then referencing the IPPC Strategic Framework should also be possible at least to explain why it is or is not being used, without implying political commitment. Her main point was not that the SRA should align to the IPPC Framework, but that the reasoning for not doing so should be transparently explained, just as the SDG link is explained.

Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) clarified that for this question he had opted for “other”, due to the unclarity between Plant Health and Phytosanitary focus.

Mr. Capiéau (CPHO Sweden, SE) followed by expressing broader concerns about the scope. He recalled the history of Euphresco, emphasizing that it was originally built to support regulatory phytosanitary activities and research needs, which are already complex and resource-limited. Expanding the SRA’s scope to encompass a wider field of plant health risks would dilute attention to core phytosanitary priorities, creating competition for funding across very different research fields, and introducing complexity just as Euphresco transitions to a global structure, which already presents challenges. He also reiterated that the pyramid diagram as presented by Ms Zorrilla (ENO, Int.) shown earlier visually suggested a clear connection to the IPPC level, and that this added to the confusion.

Mr. Giovani (ENO, Int.) acknowledged Mr. Capiéau’s concerns and emphasized that trying to implement too many changes at once may indeed be overwhelming for some members. For this reason, he views the evolution of Euphresco through a phased approach, starting with geographical expansion, consolidating and then gradually broadening the thematic scope in later iterations. Regarding the pyramid diagram, he clarified that its purpose was purely illustrative, to show how policy/standard-setting structures (IPPC) and the research-coordination network (Euphresco) exist in parallel but separately and could potentially align structurally without implying shared mandates. He reinforced that research and policy must remain distinct, partly for scientific independence and partly due to political constraints.

Session 2:

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) explained that the Session 1 group had discussed the evolution from the original Euphresco focus (phytosanitary research for Europe) toward a broader global plant health scale. She also highlighted that some participants questioned how the SRA related to the IPPC Strategic Framework, since the SRA explicitly referenced UN Sustainable Development Goals but not the IPPC framework. She also pointed out that some participants of the Session 1 group had raised concerns about whether broadening the scope could dilute attention and funding for core phytosanitary work. She stressed that the current scope statement reflects inputs from diverse consultations across regions and disciplines. She reassured participants that phytosanitary content would remain embedded within the SRA and would continue to be expressed through concrete objectives. She also emphasized that it was mentioned that the scope evolution would be gradual, not abrupt.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) added that some participants found the scope difficult to assess because the SRA’s objectives had not yet been defined. She suggested that once objectives were drafted, the scope would become clearer and easier to evaluate.

Question 5: The themes presented in the draft are...

Results summary: 80.6% considered the themes well balanced, 8.3% felt they were too broad, 5.6% said they were both too broad and too narrow, and 5.6% voted for ‘other’.

Session 1:

Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) stated that it was difficult to judge the themes without seeing the associated objectives. The themes in their current form could potentially expand in many directions, and clearer objectives would help assess their balance.

Session 2:

No comments on Question 5.

Question 6: Do you think the wording and breakdown of the themes is clear and logical? (multiple answers can be selected)

Results summary: 62.9% said the wording and breakdown were clear and logical, 17.1% felt some themes should be merged, 11.4% said some themes should be reworded, 2.9% felt some themes should be split, and 5.7% voted for ‘other’. All participants provided a single answer, except for one person (2.9% of total participants) who indicated some themes should be re-worded and some should be split.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) pointed out that “surveillance” appeared under more than one theme. She questioned whether “surveillance” should be considered a theme at all, noting that it is often an output or component of other areas rather than a stand-alone research topic. She also raised concerns about how to meaningfully define a “One Health” theme within plant health, noting a recent FAO workshop (Integrating Plant Health into One Health, 20 January 2026) suggesting that plant health does not easily generate classic One Health issues.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) confirmed that the team had taken note of the duplication of “surveillance” and would revisit how best to integrate it. Regarding One Health, she acknowledged the difficulty raised by Ms. Anthoine. Although the topic had emerged strongly during bilateral meetings, it might be more appropriate as a transversal theme. She added that she planned to contact FAO colleagues to explore possible approaches.

Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) reinforced this point by noting that further reflection needs to be undertaken in how to integrate the two transversal themes “Plant Health in a One Health context” and “Economics, Public Acceptance & Science-Policy Translation” in the SRA. Additional stakeholder input could help with guiding whether these will remain stand-alone themes or will be woven throughout the others.

Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) observed that some themes, such as “collaboration and knowledge exchange” or “capacity building,” resembled goals or strategic aims rather than research themes. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) agreed that this distinction would become clearer once objectives were drafted.

Mr. Giovani (ENO, Int.) elaborated on the strategic dimension of capacity building, explaining that research can be used either to push scientific frontiers (which only some countries are equipped for) or to build capacity across a wider set of countries. These choices reflect different roles the future network might adopt.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added that several preliminary theme titles were simply the result of clustering exercises during analysis and might evolve during refinement. They indicated conceptual areas rather than definitive research categories and as such it might be needed to use a different term than ‘themes’ in the future.

Ms. Munaut (DG SANTE, Int.) raised further concerns about overlap between themes, particularly around collaboration, capacity building, reference structures, and elements of social science. She questioned whether some themes could be merged or restructured. She also asked what was meant by “science-based regulation,” prompting Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) to explain that some regions had expressed concern about regulatory decisions relying on outdated scientific evidence, which created trade obstacles. Ms. Munaut (DG SANTE, Int.) wondered whether this issue required dedicated research or whether it should be treated as a governance question. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged that this might be better positioned as a cross-cutting aim rather than a research theme.

Ms. Oronje (CABI, Int.) observed that theme 5 (Diagnostics, Surveillance & Early Warning) and theme 10 (Preparedness, Response & Recovery) might logically belong together. In her view, diagnostics and surveillance are core components of preparedness systems, and combining these themes could strengthen coherence and avoid redundancy in the SRA.

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) agreed that the two themes share several conceptual links. She clarified, however, that theme 5 currently focuses more specifically on the development of diagnostic tools, while theme 10 deals more with response capacity and preparedness frameworks. Even so, she recognized that elements such as monitoring and early warning span both themes, and the team would examine whether merging them or more clearly distinguishing them would improve clarity.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) commented more broadly on the issue of overlap. She explained that some degree of interrelation between themes is inevitable, given the interconnected nature of plant health research. The objective-setting process would help reduce unnecessary overlap, but it would not eliminate all links between them, nor would this be aimed for.

Session 2:

Mr. Nam (INRAE, FR) proposed merging theme 5 (Diagnostics, Surveillance and Early Warning) with theme 8 (Pest Pathways, Surveillance and Risks), as well as theme 9 (Plant Health in a One Health Context) with theme 11 (Sustainable Pest Management and Biocontrol) on the grounds that these pairs addressed overlapping subject areas.

Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) welcomed this feedback and explained ongoing difficulties around transversal themes, especially One Health. The team was still unsure whether these

should exist as fully separate themes or be integrated within others. She also mentioned that the previous session suggested merging theme 5 with theme 10 (Preparedness and Response).

Ms. Day (CFIA, CA) explained that she initially voted to merge themes but, upon reflection, believed that some issues derived more from wording than structure. Especially the repeated use of “surveillance” across different theme titles, could cause confusion. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged that this duplication had indeed been noted too late and would be corrected. Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added that once detailed objectives are defined, the team will have a clearer view on whether surveillance-related concepts should belong to one theme or be separated.

Ms. Vlaminc (FPS Health, BE) asked Ms. Day for her view on whether One Health should be a theme or rather an overarching aim. Ms. Day (CFIA, CA) suggested that it might fit naturally under sustainable pest management.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added insights from notes of the previous session, reiterating that true One Health cases are rare in plant health. However, plant health could adopt tools and approaches developed in human/animal health sectors. She suggested that One Health might fit better as a transdisciplinary principle. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) added that she recently attended an FAO workshop on integrating plant health into One Health approaches, suggesting that FAO collaboration may help determine how to incorporate the concept effectively.

Ms. Vlaminc (FPS Health, BE) recalled a previous suggestion to merge theme 2 (Capacity Building and Infrastructure Development) and 4 (Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing). Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) noted that both had been flagged as aims rather than research themes in Session 1 and reiterated that the term themes might need to be replaced or differentiated into “strategic aims” versus research-oriented themes.

Question 7: The SRA will contain a dynamic component which will be adaptable to emerging plant health challenges. How often do you think this dynamic component should be reviewed? (multiple answers can be selected)

Results summary: 55.1% indicated updates ad hoc when urgent needs arise, 40.8% indicated a periodic review, and 4.1% selected ‘other’. From the detailed poll data, it was apparent that a substantial amount of people (37.1% of total participants) preferred a combined approach of periodic reviews with an additional ad hoc evaluation mechanism.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) argued strongly in favor of having both mechanisms. She said that emergencies require rapid updates, while stable periods still require periodic review to ensure objectives and priorities remain relevant. This was reiterated by Ms. Gunther (MIPHSI, PL), Mr. Mazzoni (EMF, IT), Ms. Munaut (DG SANTE, Int.), Ms. Topitschnig (AGES, AT) and Ms. Tello (INIA-CSIC, ES).

Mr. Aveskamp (NVWA, NL) explained that he had selected “other” because he felt the review frequency depended on how detailed the objectives would eventually become. Until the structure was clearer, he found it difficult to commit to either option.

Mr. Giovanni (ENO, Int.) agreed with Mr. Aveskamp and commented that the SRA is ultimately a guidance document. Because members can choose how strictly to follow it, flexibility in updating is important. He suggested that the dynamic component should not be overly prescriptive.

In response to Mr. Giovanni, Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) commented that the themes and objectives defined in the SRA will guide future call topics. Regular review is thus important for maintaining relevance.

Mr. Mazzoni (EMF, IT) also added that flexibility is important in these kinds of documents.

Session 2:

Ms. Pappas (DAFF, AU) explained that she and her colleagues believed the SRA should adopt both periodic updates and the ability to be reviewed ad-hoc when deemed necessary. She added that if the SRA were to link to the IPPC's own strategic agenda cycles, aligning review periods could be useful, depending on how strongly the SRA intends to connect to the IPPC framework.

Question 8: Within the same context, how do you think this dynamic component should be reviewed? (multiple answers can be selected)

Results summary: 29.7% selected reviews through surveys, 28.4% through workshops, 27.0% through less extensive consultations, 10.8% through extensive consultations, and 4.1% selected 'other'. Detailed poll data shows most participants indicated several answers with multiple people (37.1% of total participants) preferring a combination of workshops and surveys to carry out the consultation, be it extensive or less extensive.

Session 1:

Ms. Anthoine (DRAAF Pays-de-la-Loire, FR) asked for clarification on what “less extensive consultations” meant, whether this meant fewer stakeholders, shorter questionnaires, or something else. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) and Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) explained that this remained undefined and that stakeholder suggestions would help shape the eventual approach.

Mr. Giovanni (ENO, Int.) provided a detailed explanation of the difference between surveys and consultations. Surveys represent purely bottom-up input, while consultations merge bottom-up and top-down processes. EUPHRESKO III had used consultations to ensure policymakers and funders could refine broad stakeholder input into a focused and strategic agenda. Moving to surveys alone would remove that refinement step, either shifting the burden onto each country or onto the secretariat.

Ms. Steinhilber (JKI, DE) echoed this point and emphasized that transforming survey results into a coherent strategic agenda requires substantial effort. She recommended a combination of surveys (to gather wide input) and workshops (to synthesize it), noting that this combination might be the most efficient approach. She also reflected more broadly that for a global network, defining research priorities might become more important than managing calls, given differences in climate, pests, and regulatory contexts across world regions. She continued that while a phytosanitary scope was appropriate for the EU where regulations are harmonized, it

will not be sufficient for a global agenda. Setting up research projects will still be an important task of the future network but the most important task, in her opinion, will be discussing common research priorities. Finally, she added this shift was well mirrored in the draft of the research agenda in her opinion.

Session 2:

Ms. Day (CFIA, CA) explained that she had selected all three options (survey, workshop, less-extensive consultation). She suggested an approach starting with a preliminary survey to assess whether the SRA still meets the needs and expectations. If responses showed substantial divergence, a workshop could then be organized to refine priorities. This would maintain strategic insight while keeping the process streamlined.

Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) recalled that in the previous session, participants insisted that relying solely on surveys would be insufficient, because the original extensive survey had produced a vast amount of raw data that would be difficult to deal with without additional consultations. Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) elaborated that the survey in this project was deliberately broad to gather input from a wide array of stakeholders. However, processing such a large dataset requires live or online consultations with decision-makers and funders to interpret and prioritize the information at a higher level. She emphasized that repeating such a broad survey without a consultation step would make it nearly impossible to extract meaningful, actionable research priorities. However, a combination of a survey followed by a workshop could work as an effective update mechanism.

Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) added that a less extensive version of the survey could be used for updates, focusing only on identifying areas where revisions were needed, rather than repeating the full baseline data collection.

Question 9: Considering the dynamic component of the SRA would experience regular revisions, which format would be most practical? (multiple answers can be selected)

Results summary: 46% preferred a digital platform with interactive content, 28% preferred a permanent core document with separate addenda, 22% preferred a single comprehensive document, and 4% chose other. Here, detailed poll data again showed nearly half of all participants (44.1% of total participants) opted for several answers. In most cases (93.3% of participants who selected multiple answers; 41.2% of total participants), digital platform' was selected alongside another option.

Session 1:

Ms. Vlaminc (FPS Health, BE) shared her sentiment that she prefers having both a printable format and a digital component rather than only the latter.

Session 2:

Ms. Davie (SASA, GB) explained that she preferred a comprehensive document reuploaded after each revision because it avoids confusion about which elements have changed. She felt that multiple addenda could easily lead to misunderstandings, especially for people accessing the document quickly in policy contexts. Ms. Vlaminc (FPS Health, BE) acknowledged sharing this preference. Ms. Pappas (DAFF, AU) echoed Ms. Davie's concern in the chat, prompting Ms. Vlaminc (FPS Health, BE) to ask whether any participant firmly preferred the addenda model. Several participants indicated that a downloadable document should exist even if a digital platform is created.

Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) proposed an intermediary solution: maintain a single comprehensive document but highlight modifications between versions through color-coded changes or an introductory overview of revisions. Ms. Vlaminc (FPS Health, BE) expanded on this idea, suggesting a revision log at the beginning of the document to ensure that users immediately see whether they need to download a new version. Ms. Davie (SASA, GB) added

that an explanation of changes or options to look at previous versions could be useful but with one current comprehensive version to be most easily accessible.

Question 10: Do you think the SRA addresses the right level of ambition for global plant health research coordination?

Results summary: 76.5% said the SRA is appropriately ambitious, 20.6% said it should be less ambitious, and 2.9% selected ‘other’.

Session 1:

No comments on Question 10.

Session 2:

Mr. Park (IAPPS, Int.) highlighted that he chose “other,” as he first wished to know what “ambitious” meant in this context. Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) clarified that ambition primarily referred to the broadening of scope from strictly phytosanitary issues to a wider plant health context. Ms. Vlamincx (FPS Health, BE) added that “too ambitious” might be interpreted as the SRA needing to remain more tightly aligned with phytosanitary concerns. Ms. Nouwen (FPS Health, BE) added that ambition could also be interpreted as the feasibility of working across all the proposed themes. She observed that the current SRA is considerably broader than the previous Euphresco SRA. Participants who felt it was too ambitious might believe only a fraction of the themes could realistically be pursued. She encouraged participants to assess ambition in the general context of global research coordination, not only in comparison with the previous Euphresco SRA. Mr. Park (IAPPS, Int.) clarified in the chat that, considering this additional information, he found the current SRA appropriately ambitious.

Question 11: What additional elements would make the SRA more valuable for you? (open answer)

Participants were asked to submit their answers for this question either via the Teams chat or via e-mail (by contacting Samantha De Gottal directly). No submissions have been received for this question yet, but they are still welcome at samantha.degottal@health.fgov.be.

1.7 Future Development of the SRA – Samantha De Gottal (FPS Health, BE)

Ms. De Gottal (FPS Health, BE) concluded the webinar by outlining the next steps: integrating webinar feedback, continuing bilateral discussions with Euphresco (III) members, obtaining additional input from (non-)members and advisors, refining themes into objectives, completing SRA 1.0 by September 2026, and sharing it broadly for final comments before endorsement in late 2026.